

Customer Satisfaction of DLSUD Students on On-line Food Service Delivery

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Abstract: Since the pandemic, people are instructed to stay at home and limit themselves from going outside. Food is one of the necessities that people need and one way to get food is to buy it in the market or buy it at a food establishment. Because of the development of technology, companies such as GrabFood, FoodPanda, LalaFood, and other companies found a way to bring convenience to customers and reduce the spread of the virus by going outside. The researchers conducted a study about customer satisfaction with Online Food Service Delivery among DLSUD students to point out if customers received a good and quality standard of service from the food delivery riders. The researchers used the 4-Point Likert Scale for DLSUD students to rate their satisfaction with the Online Food Delivery Service and they also used One-Way ANOVA to compute the gathered data and determine their satisfaction with Online Food Delivery Service. The researchers found out that the DLSUD students that answered the survey were satisfied with the way they received the service by using Online Food Service Delivery. Because of the company's rapid growth and exceptional research and development, they were able to comply with the health and safety protocols and still give out good and quality service to the customers.

Keywords: RATER, Likert Scale, service quality, SERVQUAL, Food Service Delivery.

1. INTRODUCTION

Online food services developed globally as many studies show that many countries used this service to reach out to their customers. As the report of the World Online Food Delivery Industry (2019), states that online food delivery service is rapidly growing and experiencing enormous development. It likewise says that online food delivery service is developing everywhere due to their benefit, assortment, and accessible price with just mobile phone and the internet.

Locally, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) have also adopted this method as a way to connect with customers. New companies were developed specifically for online food delivery services like Foodpanda, Grab food, Lalafood, Honestbee, and many more. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) reach out to these companies to deliver the food to the customer and the business would profit by utilizing these companies as their carrier.

As demand for conveniently getting food rises, some businesses developed online food service delivery as a way to reach out to customers in a convenient way. Online food service delivery is the most useful way to reach out and connect with the customer because almost all people have mobile devices and the internet nowadays. It is easier for the people who love to eat but prefer to stay home, especially as the pandemic starts to rise and people are encouraged to stay at home. Nowadays there are a lot of small food businesses that are using online food service delivery to profit and stay afloat.

A law that seeks to ensure the satisfaction of both the customer and third-party platform is "House Bill 48–651. Third-party food delivery platforms" written by the Council of the District of Columbia. This bill acts as protection between both the customer and third-party platform that prevents the violation of the disclosed agreement between the customer and third-party platform upon purchase and delivery of food. About an article in the Philippine Government that tackles the safety of

the courier from the malicious use of the third-party delivery food platforms by customers canceling their orders is named "House Bill No. 6958" or "Food and Grocery Delivery Services Protection Act" which was proposed by Hon. Alfredo A. Garbin Jr. stated that the bill seeks to provide safeguards to the riders and penalize the customers who unreasonably, unceremoniously, and unconsciously cancel their orders. The violator will be fined 100,000.00 pesos and face six years and one day of imprisonment. Lastly, a law that provides safety to the customer and ensures the quality of the food to be delivered is "House Bill 48-653. Restrictions on Third-party meal delivery companies" written by the Council of the District of Columbia. This bill states that the collection of meals must be authorized by the restaurant before third-party meal delivery platforms are allowed to collect and deliver. This ensures that the quality and health protocols are to be observed upon preparing and delivery of a meal and that food and beverages prepared by a restaurant would be picked up and delivered within the same day. These laws not only aim to satisfy but also protect the customer and give them transparency upon the use of the On-line Food Delivery Service.

Background of the Study:

As modern era approaches, people nowadays are looking for convenient way to grab food and businesses are innovating their service. According to Das (2018), he stated that technology has played a key part in revolutionizing the food delivery service. It has contributed to the changes in consumers preference or liking as their dependency of technology has motivated people to do everything online comprising getting cooked meals delivered to their doorstep. The interaction and transformation between online (virtual) and offline (virtual) food businesses determines the dynamic development of future food shopping (Lau and Ng 2019). Online food delivery service has emerged into the local scene because of it is way more efficient than going to the establishment and it is user friendly since it is easy to order food products in a restaurant using the application. According to Andal et.al (2022), Food ordering applications such as GrabFood, TokTok, Delivery Guy PH, and Food Panda are examples of the newfound popularity of food delivery services. Even fast-food chains have their food ordering applications such as McDonald's, Jollibee, Shakey's, Greenwhich, and some well-known fast-food chains or restaurants in the Philippines.

Online food delivery service in the Philippines is particularly new and it has emerged when the pandemic started. People has since used online food delivery applications to save time on their work and for students, it can save time working for their academics. People has different perceptions on service quality of online food delivery service as a general. Theoretically, online food delivery service companies are still developing and improving their service quality to their customers.

This study is conducted to show how DLSUD students perceived online food delivery service as a general. Some students nowadays have been using online food delivery application and experienced online food delivery service. Therefore, the researchers conducted this study to know how they perceive and rate the overall service quality of online food delivery service base on reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, and responsiveness.

Statement of the Study:

The aim of this study is to assess customer satisfaction of DLSUD community towards online food delivery service. Also, this study can furthermore improve the service of businesses that uses on-line food delivery to improve the customer satisfaction.

Statement of the Problem:

1. Demographic profile of the respondents
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Educational Attainment
 - 1.4 Budget/ Allowance
2. How do the respondents assess their experience in terms of:
 - 2.1 Reliability
 - 2.2 Assurance
 - 2.3 Tangibles

2.4 Empathy

2.5 Responsiveness

3. Is there a significance relationship between demographic profile of the respondents and service quality rating of the restaurant?

4. What quality service program can be proposed to address the motivations or intentions to return the guests of the restaurants?

Conceptual Framework:

Figure 1: IPO Method (Moena et al, 2013)

The researchers chose the IPO method as conceptual framework because running an online food delivery service has factors to be considered to function well. According to Moena, et al (2013), IPO method is an information processing cycle that determines how the information is processed and handled with in a system. IPO system is always used in a business because every company has its own end product or output.

Figure 2: SERVQUAL Model

The researchers also used “Servqual Model” as a supporting framework because it determines the quality of the service of a company. It also focuses more on how the customer perceives online food delivery service. According to Arora & Narula (2018), this Servqual instrument has been the predominant method used to measure consumers’ perception of service quality.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

According to Nayan and Hassan (2020), Online food delivery services have an important and major role in customers experience. Customer satisfaction involved many factors, such as availability of food, customer ratings, payment methods, and human interaction. They also stated that to achieve maximum customer satisfaction, service providers need to focus on the quality of service and the definite goal of food delivery services should be to have maximum customer satisfaction and not just only profit. Consumer satisfaction with the delivery of online food is an indicator of how a company’s service is delivered to meet customer needs (Azman et. al. 2021).

As stated by Chai and Yat (2019), Online food delivery (OFD) service is an emerging new wave within the food and beverage industry in Malaysia. The emergence of online food delivery services could be attributed to the changing nature of urban consumers. Technology has played a big role in revolutionizing the food delivery service from phone-based to online ordering to satisfying consumers' ever-changing demands, making its way to the top. Technology has also contributed to the changes in consumer preferences as their dependence on technology has moved them to do everything online including getting cooked meals delivered to their doorstep (See-Kwong et.al. 2017). Online food delivery service refers to internet-based food ordering delivery services that connects to customers with partner foodservice operations via their websites or mobile applications. Online food delivery services provide a wide range of restaurant lists, allowing customers to compare menus, prices, and even reviews from other users by restaurant types (Jun et.al 2021).

The term Service Quality is an association of two different words: "service" and "quality". Service means "any activity or benefit that one party can offer to another that is essentially intangible and does not result in the ownership of anything". Quality has come to be recognized as a strategic tool for attaining operational efficiency and better performance of business (Ramya, Kowsalya and Dharanipriya, 2019). Quality service is being perceived by the customer according to Reliability, Assurance, Tangibility, Empathy and Responsiveness. Kotler and Armstrong defined "service quality" as ability of a service firm to satisfy or hang on to the customer (Ramya, Kowsalya and Dharanipriya, 2019). There are three ways to assess service quality, using SERVQUAL, Service quality questionnaires and Service quality questions. SERVQUAL measures the rating of reliability, assurance, tangible, empathy and responsiveness. This ensures that it measures the gap between customers' expectation and perception of the actual service delivered. Second is service quality questionnaires, this can be done by asking feedback to customers using questionnaires. Typically, it uses email or paper survey. Last is service quality questions, this focus on the interaction to customer and asking about the overall experience about their service (Qualtrics, 2020). There is a law where it protects riders to customers who cancel their orders with no genuine intention of availing the product. House Bill No. 6958 or the Food and Grocery Delivery Services seeks to protect riders and penalize customers who unreasonably, unceremoniously, and unconsciously cancel their order which is created by Hon. Alfredo A. Garbin Jr. (Mercado, 2020).

It measures the service quality being provided to the customer and it is essentially form structure market research that splits into five areas or dimensions of service quality (Fripp, 2017). RATER framework evolved from SERVQUAL study created by psychologists Parasurman, Zeithaml and Berry in 1988 (SimpleSAT, 2020).

Participants of the Study

The participants of this study are De La Salle University - Dasmariñas students who have experienced ordering food through online. The researchers specifically chose this respondent for precise evaluation about online food delivery service.

The number of the respondents will be consulted by the assigned statistician to the researchers. The researchers target value of respondents will be 300 students. Suppose that the researchers' target value is 90 respondents and given that the response rate to chosen students is 30%. Then the researchers should invite about 300 respondents for this study. The formula in getting our target respondents is $90 \text{ respondents} / 30\% \text{ response rate} \times 100 = 300 \text{ respondents}$ (CloudResearch, 2022)

Locale of the Study

The study will be conducted at the De La Salle University Campus only. The researchers preferred this specific location to conduct this study to limit the scope and limitations to only students of DLSUD. The participant's requirement is to have experience ordering food through online and which is inclined to answer the researcher's survey.

3. METHODOLOGY

The researchers decided to use quantitative method as the research design and will make use of Likert scale as criteria for measuring the customer satisfaction towards online food delivery service. Quantitative research design emphasizes objective measurements and uses statistical method to solve and to find the numerical data needed (Babbie 2010).

Sampling Method

The researchers will use Purposive Sampling as their sampling method. As this method will ensure that the researcher respondents have already experienced using online food delivery service. This will ensure that the data being collected is precise and useful. According to Crossman (2020), Purposive Sampling can be very useful in situations when you need to reach a targeted sample quickly, and where sampling proportionality is not the main concern.

4. DATA GATHERING & ANALYSIS

For data gathering, the researchers created a survey that will provide data and information about their perception and experience to online food delivery service. The instrument that the researchers will use to conduct the study is online survey forms using Google forms. This will be passed on to the respondents to gather data based on their experience on using online food delivery service.

The survey that are being conducted used Likert scale in gathering data. According to McLeod (2019), Likert scale was developed to measure attitudes directly. The scale that the researchers will use is the 4-point Likert scale as this scale can report exactly how many were satisfied and how many were not. According to Hopper (2016), 4-point Likert scale can be split into simple dichotomies which includes how many agree vs how many disagree, how many were interested vs not-interested and how many are likely vs not likely and so on.

After gathering all the data and information needed, the researchers would calculate the frequency of the demographics based on the collected data and distribute the variables, and lastly rank them based on their frequency. According to Hoyland (2021), frequency is the number of times a data value occurs. Frequency distribution on the other hand represents the frequencies of the set of data values being examined.

After getting the frequency of demographics, next is to get the mean based on online food delivery service and interpret the tabulated data. According to Wei (2021), statistical mean is an arithmetic mean process, it adds up all numbers in a data set, and then divides the by the number of data points.

Lastly is to conduct tests such as Mann-Whitney U test for interpret if there is difference pertaining online food delivery service based on gender. Stated by Wilson (2022), Mann-Whitney U test is a non-parametric test that is used to work around the underlying assumption of normality in parametric tests

One-Way ANOVA test were used to tabulate the data of service quality based on their age, educational attainment, and budget allowance. As stated by Mackenzie (2018), One-Way ANOVA is a type of statistical test that compares the variance in the group means within a sample whilst considering only one independent variable or factor. He also mentioned that One-Way ANOVA compares three or more than categorical groups to establish whether there is a difference between them.

Since the researchers conducted a Quantitative research, the researchers' statistician has utilized R – Project software to tabulate the data that the researchers gathered during the data gathering process. According to Solanki (2017), R is an open-source software development programming language, which was developed by Ross Ihaka and Robert Gentleman in New Zealand in 1991. It is a programming language, which can be used in statistical analysis and in technical research work.

5. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The researchers gathered data using Google forms survey and using 4-point Likert scale as a scale to determine exactly how many were satisfied in using On-Line Food Service Delivery. The respondents assess their experience in terms of Reliability, Empathy, Assurance, Tangibles, Responsiveness, and Service Quality.

Table 1.1: Age Frequency

Age	Frequency	Relative Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
16-18 years old	34	0.11	11.3%	2
19-23 years old	247	0.82	82.3%	1
24 years old and above	19	0.06	6.3%	3
Total	300	1.00	100%	

The demographic profile based on their age as shown in Table 1.1 shows that majority of the respondent's age are 19 – 23 years old with 247 respondents which has percentage of 82.3%. The least among the age groups are 24 years old and above. It shows that young adults or millennials used application such as GrabFood ,FoodPanda ,etc. and has experienced online food delivery service.

This age group appreciate the comfort of having the food delivered into their homes. This takes the hassle to go to restaurants to order food and dine in the establishment. Because of the pandemic, it is much safer to eat at their comfort of their home to avoid getting the virus.

According to Silver (2020), Millennials are three times more likely to order in than their parents. This makes them the largest demographic for food delivery applications.

Table 1.2: Gender Frequency

Gender	Frequency	Relative Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
Male	174	0.58	58%	1
Female	126	0.42	42%	2
Total	300	1.00	100%	

The demographic profile based on their gender as shown in Table 1.2 shows that male respondents have already experienced online food delivery service with a percentage of 58% while the female has a percentage of 42%. It shows that men usually use online food delivery application and experienced online food delivery service.

Men order frequently use online food delivery application to satisfy their cravings and hunger and because of this, they tend to go to restaurants or order food through online food delivery application.

According to Norris (2019), Men usually order more in the late hours of the day as compared to women (10 p.m. to 2 a.m.). Male are 55% more likely to order than women. But as for location, if they are nearby the restaurant, male prefer to pick up their food from restaurants while women prefer to order their food online from their workplace.

Table 1.3: Educational Attainment Frequency

Year Level	Frequency	Relative Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
Grade 11	7	0.02	2.3%	6
Grade 12	25	0.08	8.3%	4
1 st year College	34	0.11	11.3%	3
2 nd year College	90	0.30	30%	2
3 rd year College	126	0.42	42%	1
4 th year College	18	0.06	6%	5
Total	300	1.00	100%	

The demographic profile according to their educational attainment as shown in Table 1.3 shows that 3rd year college students are the most people who order food through online food delivery application with a percentage of 42%. On the other hand, the least are grade 11 students with a percentage of 2.3%. It shows that 3rd year college students often use online food delivery application and experienced online food delivery service.

College students mostly 3rd year college students often value time because of their hectic class schedules, school assessments, exams, etc. By ordering food online, they save time, and it is way more convenient rather than ordering food into the restaurant.

According to an article of American Dining Creations (2022), College students need to keep their physical and mental health up. Offering quick, convenient, and contactless takeout or delivery options can make eating right more manageable for students. They can then continue focusing on their studies instead of worrying about how to receive meals during the pandemic safely.

Table 1.4: Budget/Allowance Frequency

Budget/Allowance	Frequency	Relative Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
100 – 500 pesos	170	0.56	56.0%	1
500 – 1000 pesos	105	0.35	35.0%	2
1000 – 2500 pesos	25	0.08	8.3%	3
Total	300	1.00	100%	

The demographic profile according to their budget/allowance as shown in table 1.4 shows that majority of students have a budget/allowance of 100 – 500 pesos to spend on food. The lowest among the budget/allowance is 1000 – 5000 pesos. It shows that students they have between 100 – 500 pesos to spend on food on ordering food through online food delivery service.

In researcher's theory, students often order food online for themselves and their are mostly saving their allowances just to save up to order food online in other day. Most restaurants offer food that are cheap or just enough for students to buy their products.

According to Villareal (2017), students are willing to invest less than 20 euros which is equivalent to 1,130 pesos to buy good food online. Different students in different countries with different majors have one common factor; They have similar eating habits. Nowadays, students live in a fast-paced environment where time matters.

Table 2.1: Reliability

Descriptive	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Reliability: Serves food as indicated by quality and standards.	3.38	Agree	1
Reliability: Prioritizes customer satisfaction employee	3.03	Agree	4
Reliability: Open to any concerns of the customer for the delivery.	2.99	Agree	5
Reliability: On time delivery, depending on the place.	3.05	Agree	3
Reliability: Accuracy of the billing statement of the production.	3.32	Agree	2
Overall Assessment of Reliability	3.154	High	

1.00-1.49 - Strongly Disagree, 1.50-2.49 - Disagree, 2.50-3.49 - Agree, 3.50-4.00 – Strongly Agree

It is shown in table 2.1 that the highest mean is that employee serves food as indicated by quality and standards with a mean of 3.38 equivalent to Agree. The researchers observed that most food delivered to customers were preserved the quality and standards.

According to Gell (2021), restaurants and other establishment should prioritize and better meet expectation of the customers. He also stated that restaurants can include survey questions pertaining to factors such as delivery speed, food quality, overall price, reviews and recommendation, lastly customer service.

The lowest mean in the table is that employee should be open to any concerns of the customer for the delivery. This connects to empathy as it pertains they should be reliable enough to entertain customer's concern on the delivery.

According to Chotigo and Kadono (2021), satisfaction is critical for the intention to use food delivery application. They stated that social influence, trust, convenience, and application quality were found to play an essential role the needs of satisfaction toward the intention to use, and application quality is the most important.

Table 2.2: Assurance

Descriptive	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Assurance: Knowing proper delivery consumption.	3.42	Agree	1
Assurance: Accessibility of the order to the website/application.	3.00	Agree	5
Assurance: Double checked the product before pulling out.	3.16	Agree	3
Assurance: Questions of the customers are answered well of the delivery assistance.	3.09	Agree	4
Assurance: Has a well-trained employee	3.17	Agree	2
Overall Assessment of Assurance	3.168	High	

1.00-1.49 - Strongly Disagree, 1.50-2.49 - Disagree, 2.50-3.49 - Agree, 3.50-4.00 – Strongly Agree

It is shown in the table 2.2 that employees knowing proper delivery consumption has the mean of 3.42 equivalent to Agree. The researchers observed that most employees know the proper delivery consumption of the food products that they deliver to customers.

Restaurant should check inspection scores, being aware of delivery times as cooked meals can make you sick if they sit out for more than 2 hours, or as little of 1 hour if it's 90°F or warmer outside. Lastly, leftovers or are saving a hot food delivery for another day should be refrigerate within 2 hours as stated in the article by Center for Disease Control and Prevention (2022).

The lowest mean in the table is the accessibility of the order to the website/application. The researchers observed that once the order has been placed, sometimes it cannot be edited or make some changes in the order.

To make the ordering process as smooth as possible, you must be accessible on all platforms, including websites, mobile applications and social media as stated by Batra (2022).

Table 2.3: Tangibles

Descriptive	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Tangibles: Appearance of service personnel	3.16	Agree	4
Tangibles: Appearance of tools or equipment used to provide service.	3.04	Agree	5
Tangibles: Provide utensils along with food packaging.	3.27	Agree	3
Tangibles: Packaging of the product was good quality.	3.40	Agree	1
Tangibles: Legible receipt still be provided and the accuracy of the charge fee.	3.34	Agree	2
Overall Assessment of Tangibles	3.242	High	

1.00-1.49 - Strongly Disagree, 1.50-2.49 - Disagree,
2.50-3.49 - Agree, 3.50-4.00 – Strongly Agree

It is shown in the table 2.3 that the highest mean is that the packaging of the product was good quality with a mean of 3.40 equivalent to Agree. The researchers observed that most delivered food were well packaged when they were delivered to customers.

According to Tiuttu et.al (2020), Packaging has a purpose why it is there. It provides protection, safety, enhanced usability, attractive looks, optimal design and specific customer requirements.

The lowest mean in the table is the appearance of tools or equipment used to provide service. The researchers observed some delivery employees or riders sometimes don't have the appropriate equipment and tools to deliver food products.

For the best takeout and delivery services you must have holding equipment, insulated food carriers, containers, packaging, and lastly safety equipment as stated by Kohn-Megibow Company (2020).

Table 2.4: Empathy

Descriptive	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Empathy: Gives good communication towards the customer	3.25	Agree	1
Empathy: Listening to the customer needs.	2.94	Agree	4
Empathy: Providing a personalized attention towards customer.	2.86	Agree	5

Empathy: Understanding the customers' feedback.	2.95	Agree	3
Empathy: Caring about the customers need.	3.01	Agree	2
Overall Assessment of Empathy	3.002	High	

1.00-1.49 - Strongly Disagree, 1.50-2.49 - Disagree, 2.50-3.49 - Agree, 3.50-4.00 – Strongly Agree

It is shown in table 2.4 that the highest mean is that employees gives good communication towards the customer with a mean of 3.25 equivalent to Agree. The researcher observed that employee and delivery riders gives good communication to their customers.

According to Feldman (2020), He listed five communication features essential for food delivery application which are In-App Text Messaging, In-App Calling, Delivery Status Notifications, Special Instructions and Comments on Orders, and lastly is Push Notifications. This list should prevent customers from getting frustrated and dissatisfied with the outcome of their orders.

The lowest mean in the table is that providing a personalized attention towards customer with a mean of 2.86. The researchers observed that some employees or rather some restaurants don't provide personalized attention towards customer.

According to Newman (2016), The need for personalization in customer service has become more pronounced now since customers are now a more demanding and fastidious "breed". She also stated that the customers expect to be treated well and receive individual attention with so many competitors for a single company, customers know that companies will comply.

Table 2.5: Responsiveness

Descriptive	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Responsiveness: Satisfactory in terms of contacting/ordering from the establishment.	3.26	Agree	1
Responsiveness: Having short time waiting for the delivery.	3.01	Agree	5
Responsiveness: Was the call handled well by the customer service	3.08	Agree	2
Responsiveness: Quality of the call with regards to placing orders	3.07	Agree	3
Responsiveness: Willingness to help customer.	3.06	Agree	4
Overall Assessment of Responsiveness	3.096	High	

1.00-1.49 - Strongly Disagree, 1.50-2.49 - Disagree, 2.50-3.49 - Agree, 3.50-4.00 – Strongly Agree

It is shown in the table 2.5 that the highest mean is satisfactory in terms of contacting/ordering from the establishment with a mean of 3.26 equivalent to Agree. The researchers observed that customers can contact easily through using the application in which it is more convenient to communicate using the application.

According to Feldman (2020), third-party delivery platforms have enabled rapid expansion in the food ordering application market, but restaurants are still looking for ways to improve their customer service in what's becoming an impersonal business.

The lowest mean in the table is having short time waiting for the delivery with the mean of 3.01. The researchers observed that delivery riders or employees take time to deliver their food into their homes. Traffic may affect the delivery time and customers should be considerate to the delivery rider/employee.

According to Gyaan (2020), to furthermore improve delivery times is to assign orders and track deliveries with technology. Using the application, delivery riders could accept orders from customers through online when they are nearby the restaurant and nearby the address of the customer. Lastly is for customers to give proper address and have communication. They can do this using the online food delivery application for clear communication.

Service Quality	F	df1	df2	p	Interpretation
Reliability	0.719	2	36.2	0.494	Not Significant
Assurance	1.435	2	36.8	0.251	Not Significant
Tangibles	1.084	2	39.0	0.348	Not Significant
Empathy	0.502	2	38.2	0.609	Not Significant
Responsiveness	1.110	2	38.1	0.340	Not Significant

Interpretation: Based on table 3.1, the data states that there is no recorded significant difference based on respondent's rating pertaining service quality of online food delivery service. Since all the variables pertaining service quality has a p-value greater than 0.05, then the null hypothesis is not rejected. The respondents regardless of their age have the same assessment on reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, and responsiveness of the service quality of online food delivery service.

Table 3.2: Independent Sample T-test based on Gender

Year Level	Test	Sum of Ranks	P	Interpretation
Reliability	Mann-Whitney U	10701	0.722	Not Significant
Assurance	Mann-Whitney U	10894	0.926	Not Significant
Tangibles	Mann-Whitney U	10551	0.576	Not Significant
Empathy	Mann-Whitney U	10594	0.616	Not Significant
Responsiveness	Mann-Whitney U	10318	0.377	Not Significant

Interpretation: Based on the table 3.2, the data states that there is no recorded significant difference based on respondent's rating pertaining service quality of online food delivery service. Since all the variables pertaining service quality has a p-value greater than 0.05, then the null hypothesis is not rejected. The respondents regardless of their gender have the same assessment on reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, and responsiveness of the service quality of online food delivery service.

Table 3.3: Grouped by Educational Attainment

Service Quality	F	df1	df2	p	Interpretation
Reliability	2.27	5	294	0.047	Significant
Assurance	2.50	5	294	0.031	Significant
Tangibles	3.17	5	294	0.008	Significant
Empathy	2.88	5	294	0.015	Significant
Responsiveness	2.56	5	294	0.028	Significant

Interpretation: Based on the table 3.3, the data states that there is a recorded significant difference based on respondent’s rating pertaining service quality of online food delivery service. Since all the variables pertaining service quality has a p-value greater than 0.05, this means that there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The respondents based on their educational attainment has different assessment on reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, responsiveness of the service quality of online food delivery service.

Table 3.4: Grouped by Budget/Allowance

Service Quality	F	df1	df2	p	Interpretation
Reliability	0.377	2	297	0.686	Not Significant
Assurance	1.099	2	297	0.334	Not Significant
Tangibles	0.930	2	297	0.396	Not Significant
Empathy	3.379	2	297	0.035	Significant
Responsiveness	4.025	2	297	0.019	Significant

Interpretation: Based on table 3.4, the tabulated data states that reliability, assurance, and tangibles recorded no significant differences while empathy and responsiveness has recorded significant differences. Based on the interpretation, the researchers reject the null hypothesis of empathy and responsiveness while the null hypothesis of reliability, assurance, and tangibles have no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The respondents based on their budget/allowance has different assessment on reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, responsiveness of the service quality of online food delivery service.

Proposed Quality Service Program to Address the Motivations or Intentions to return the guests of the Restaurants

Demographics:

Based on the demographic profile, online food delivery service application has less impact on students who are ages 16 – 18 years old and 24 years old and above. The researchers suggest marketing the application to students who are ages 16 – 18 years old 24 years old and above and promote the use of online food delivery service. By doing this, they can maximize the profits of their business using online food delivery applications while pandemic and post-pandemic.

Most users of the online food delivery application are male students according to the tabulated data that was recorded. The researchers suggest to market promotions that includes to fascinate both male and female customers. The marketing team should connect the needs and behavior of both genders so both can enjoy using online food delivery application.

Most users of online food delivery applications are 2nd year college and 3rd year college students, and it is suggested that they maximize promoting the application in all students as it provides sales as a third-party channel and other restaurants. Also, it is one way for students to value their time and ensure their safety during pandemic.

Lastly, majority of students have a budget/allowance of 100 – 500 pesos in spending in ordering food using online food delivery applications. The least in the result is budget/allowance between 1000 – 2500 pesos. The researchers suggested that restaurants should create promotions that promotes buying food products that will make students to spend more than usual. As for online food delivery application, the online food delivery company should create promos and loyalty programs for customers spending more using their application.

Rater Scale

Most of the data tabulated in the questionnaire got a good score and good interpretation based on service quality pertaining online food delivery service. There is still a possibility for furthermore improvement on overall service quality of online food delivery service.

Assurance

It is suggested that online food delivery application is well maintained and easy to access for customers to order their food online. This ensures that customers will not have a hard time ordering food using online food delivery application.

Empathy

It is suggested that restaurants should listen to customers' needs and having personalized attention towards customer if needed. Some customers may request additional things to a restaurant when ordering and some may personalize their order depending on the customer's preferences. If the establishment can entertain the customer's request, then it may show that the establishment empathize with the customer.

Tangibles

It is suggested that the employee or delivery rider should checked if all the necessary utensils are complete, and the packaging of the food is well packaged and ready for delivery. In this way, the customers are ensuring that the food would not be ruined during the delivery process.

Empathy

It is suggested that restaurants should listen to customers' needs and having personalized attention towards customer if needed. Some customers may request additional things to a restaurant when ordering and some may personalize their order depending on the customer's preferences. If the establishment can entertain the customer's request, then it may show that the establishment empathize with the customer.

Responsiveness

It is suggested that delivery riders should accept order when they are nearby the restaurant or establishment and nearby the customer's address. This ensures that the delivery time will be short and ensures that the food will not be ruined or spoiled during the delivery process.

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